

The Structural and Functional Echocardiographic Changes in Haemodialysis Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease: A Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

ARTICLE DETAILS

Objectives

To determine the prevalence and types of echocardiographic abnormalities in end-stage renal disease (ESRD) patients on hemodialysis and assess their association with clinical comorbidities.

Background

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD), especially those undergoing hemodialysis. Cardiac structural and functional abnormalities such as left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) and diastolic dysfunction are highly prevalent but often underdiagnosed.

Methods

This cross-sectional descriptive study enrolled 120 adult patients undergoing regular hemodialysis for ≥ 3 months. Standard transthoracic echocardiography, including 2D, Doppler, and global longitudinal strain (GLS), was performed. Associations between echocardiographic abnormalities and clinical parameters including hypertension and diabetes mellitus were analyzed using the chi-square test.

Results

Echocardiography revealed LV hypertrophy in 58.3% of patients, diastolic dysfunction in 66.7%, and systolic dysfunction in 15.8%. Mean GLS was $12 \pm 3.09\%$. Hypertension was significantly associated with LVH ($p < 0.001$), increased LA volume index ($p < 0.001$), diastolic dysfunction ($p < 0.001$), and impaired GLS ($p < 0.001$). Diabetes showed no statistically significant association with echocardiographic abnormalities.

Conclusions

Structural and functional cardiac changes are common in hemodialysis patients, especially in those with hypertension. Early identification via echocardiography, including strain imaging, is essential for cardiovascular risk stratification in this population.

Condensed Abstract

In 120 CKD patients on hemodialysis, echocardiography revealed a high prevalence of LVH, diastolic dysfunction, and subclinical systolic dysfunction. Hypertension was significantly correlated with adverse remodeling and strain impairment. These findings support routine echocardiographic monitoring in dialysis patients.

KEYWORDS: Chronic Kidney Disease; Haemodialysis; Echocardiography; Left Ventricular Hypertrophy; Diastolic Dysfunction; Global Longitudinal Strain; Pulmonary Hypertension

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Clinical Perspectives

Competency in Medical Knowledge

Patients with CKD on hemodialysis frequently develop subclinical cardiac dysfunction. Echocardiography, particularly with GLS, identifies myocardial impairment before Ejection Fraction declines.

Translational Outlook

Integrating echocardiographic surveillance into CKD care could facilitate early intervention, potentially reducing the cardiovascular burden in this vulnerable population.

CENTRAL ILLUSTRATION

Figure 1: Baseline clinical characteristics of CKD patients on Haemodialysis

Figure 2: Prevalence of Abnormal Echocardiographic Findings in Haemodialysis Patients

It clearly demonstrates that abnormal GLS (70.8%), diastolic dysfunction (66.7%), LA enlargement (60%), and LVH (58.3%) are the most common abnormalities.

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Structural and Functional Echocardiographic Changes in Haemodialysis Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease: A Cross-Sectional Study

INTRODUCTION

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a global public health burden, affecting over 850 million individuals worldwide and projected to become the fifth leading cause of death by 2040. Cardiovascular disease (CVD) remains the primary cause of death among CKD patients, accounting for more than 40% of all-cause mortality in dialysis populations [1].

Patients with ESRD are particularly prone to LVH, myocardial fibrosis and dysfunction due to volume overload, hypertension, anaemia, arteriovenous fistula flow, and uremic toxins. These abnormalities are often asymptomatic but may progress to heart failure, arrhythmia, and sudden cardiac death [2].

Echocardiography is a valuable noninvasive tool for assessing cardiac structure and function in CKD. GLS adds further value by detecting subtle myocardial impairment before ejection fraction (EF) decreases. Despite this, data from low- and middle-income countries on the burden of echocardiographic abnormalities in haemodialysis patients remain limited [3].

This study aimed to characterize structural and functional echocardiographic changes in CKD patients on maintenance haemodialysis and explore associations with clinical variables such as hypertension and diabetes.

METHODS

Study Design and Population

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the No. (1) 700 Bedded Hospital, Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar, from March 2024 to April 2025. A total of 120 adult patients with ESRD on maintenance haemodialysis (≥ 3 months) were consecutively enrolled.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Eligible participants were adults (≥ 18 years) with a diagnosis of ESRD undergoing regular maintenance haemodialysis who provided written informed consent. We excluded patients with known structural heart disease unrelated to chronic kidney disease, a myocardial infarction within the preceding 3 months, or an inadequate echocardiographic window precluding reliable assessment.

Data Collection

Demographic and clinical data (age, sex, comorbidities, blood pressure, laboratory values) were collected. Comprehensive transthoracic echocardiography was performed using standardized protocols based on American Society of Echocardiography recommendations [17,20].

Echocardiographic assessment

Echocardiographic assessment included indexed left ventricular (LV) mass and relative wall thickness, left atrial volume index, diastolic function (E/A ratio, E/e', LAVI), systolic function (LVEF and GLS), valvular abnormalities, right heart function (TAPSE, RVSP), and the presence of pericardial effusion. GLS was measured using speckle-

tracking echocardiography with apical 4-, 2-, and 3-chamber views. A value of $<16\%$ was considered abnormal [17,20].

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

SPSS version 25.0 was used. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm SD; categorical variables as percentages. Associations between clinical variables and echocardiographic findings were assessed using Pearson's Chi-square test. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

ETHICS

Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board. All participants provided written informed consent.

RESULTS

Baseline Characteristics

Among 120 participants, mean age was 49.7 ± 14.1 years; 69.2% were female. Hypertension was present in 50.8%, diabetes in 25.8%, and anaemia in 71.7%.

Table 1: Baseline clinical characteristics of CKD patients on Haemodialysis

Variable Value	Frequency (%)
Age (mean \pm SD)	49.7 ± 14.1 years
Male/Female	30.8% / 69.2%
Hypertension	61 (50.8%)
Diabetes mellitus	31 (25.8%)
Hyperlipidaemia	72 (60.0%)
Anaemia	86 (71.7%)
Hypocalcaemia	45 (37.5%)
Hyperphosphatemia	36 (30.0%)

DISCUSSION

Baseline Characteristics

The baseline profile of our haemodialysis cohort reflects a high prevalence of traditional and CKD-related cardiovascular risk factors. The mean age was 49.7 ± 14.1 years, with a predominance of female patients (69.2%). Comorbid conditions such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, anaemia, hyperlipidaemia, hypocalcaemia, and hyperphosphatemia were commonly observed.

Hypertension

Hypertension was present in 50.8% of patients, consistent with global data indicating that 50–80% of haemodialysis patients are hypertensive [4]. In the Dialysis Outcomes and Practice Patterns Study (DOPPS), uncontrolled hypertension remained prevalent despite dialysis adequacy [5]. Chronic pressure overload contributes significantly to LV hypertrophy and diastolic dysfunction, which was confirmed in our cohort where hypertension was strongly associated with echocardiographic abnormalities ($p < 0.001$).

Structural and Functional Echocardiographic Changes in Haemodialysis Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease: A Cross-Sectional Study

Diabetes Mellitus

Diabetes mellitus was seen in 25.8% of patients, which is slightly lower than rates reported in Western cohorts, where 35–45% of dialysis patients have diabetes [6]. For instance, the United States Renal Data System (USRDS) reported that 40% of U.S. patients initiating dialysis had diabetes as the primary cause of ESRD [7]. Although diabetes is a well-known cardiovascular risk factor, our study found weaker associations with echocardiographic abnormalities, possibly due to sample size and variations in glycaemic control.

Hyperlipidaemia

Hyperlipidaemia was reported in 60% of participants, higher than the 40–50% prevalence typically described in North American and European cohort [8]. Dyslipidaemia in CKD is characterized by elevated triglycerides and low HDL cholesterol, both of which accelerate vascular calcification and myocardial fibrosis. This may have contributed indirectly to the structural cardiac changes we observed [8].

Anaemia

Anaemia was one of the most striking findings, affecting 71.7% of patients. This aligns with previous studies indicating that 60–80% of haemodialysis patients suffer from anaemia [9]. Zoccali et al. demonstrated that anaemia contributes to LVH and impaired diastolic relaxation through increased cardiac output and myocardial oxygen demand [10]. The high prevalence in our cohort likely contributed to the burden of LVH and diastolic dysfunction.

Disorders of Mineral Metabolism

Hypocalcaemia (37.5%) and hyperphosphatemia (30%) were prevalent in our patients, consistent with disturbances in bone-mineral metabolism described in CKD-MBD (chronic kidney disease–mineral bone disorder) [11]. These abnormalities promote vascular calcification, arterial stiffness, and LV dysfunction. International guidelines, including KDIGO, emphasize the control of calcium and phosphate to mitigate cardiovascular risk in CKD [12].

Smoking

Smoking was reported in 15.6% of participants, lower than global averages for dialysis cohorts (14–20%) [13]. Even modest smoking prevalence in CKD patients has been associated with accelerated atherosclerosis and increased cardiovascular morbidity [13].

Comparison with International Cohorts

Compared to large international studies such as DOPPS and the CRIC study, our cohort appears younger, with a lower prevalence of diabetes but a higher prevalence of anaemia and hyperlipidaemia [5,6]. These variations may reflect regional differences in ESRD aetiology, dietary factors, and healthcare access. The absence of significant associations with diabetes, anaemia, hyperlipidaemia, hypocalcaemia, and hyperphosphatemia in our cohort is most likely due to a combination of limited sample size, high prevalence of these

conditions (reducing group contrasts), and the dominant role of hypertension. Longitudinal multicenter studies with larger populations may better clarify the relative contributions of these risk factors [5,6].

Clinical Implications

The clustering of hypertension, anaemia, and mineral metabolism disorders in our cohort underscores the multifactorial cardiovascular burden faced by haemodialysis patients. Addressing these modifiable risk factors through optimized dialysis, pharmacologic therapy, and lifestyle interventions may help reduce the high prevalence of cardiac remodelling observed in our echocardiographic analysis.

Table 2: Echocardiographic Findings

Echocardiographic Findings	
Echocardiographic Parameter	Abnormal (%)
LV Hypertrophy	70 (58.3%)
Left Atrial Volume Index	30 ± 4.25
Diastolic Dysfunction	80 (66.7%)
Systolic Dysfunction	19 (15.8%)
GLS <16%	85 (70.8%)
Mitral Regurgitation	20 (16.7%)
Tricuspid Regurgitation	10 (8.3%)
Pulmonary Hypertension	12 (10%)
Pericardial Effusion	18 (15%)
TAPSE <16 mm	8 (8.7%)
Mean GLS:	12 ± 3.09%
Mean RVSP:	55 ± 8.73 mmHg

Association with Clinical Variables

Hypertension was significantly associated with:

- LVH: 78.7% vs. 37.3% ($p < 0.001$)
- RWT: 68.9% vs. 39.0% ($p = 0.001$)
- Diastolic dysfunction: 83.6% vs. 49.2% ($p < 0.001$)
- Systolic dysfunction: 27.9% vs. 3.4% ($p < 0.001$)
- GLS abnormality: 86.9% vs. 54.2% ($p < 0.001$)

Diabetes mellitus showed non-significant trends toward higher prevalence of dysfunction but lacked statistical significance (e.g., GLS abnormal in 83.9% of diabetics vs. 66.3% of non-diabetics, $p = 0.065$).

DISCUSSION

In this cross-sectional echocardiographic study of patients with ESRD on maintenance haemodialysis, we found a high burden of structural and functional cardiac abnormalities. LVH, diastolic dysfunction, and impaired GLS were the most prevalent findings. Hypertension was the strongest clinical factor associated with these echocardiographic abnormalities.

Structural and Functional Echocardiographic Changes in Haemodialysis Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease: A Cross-Sectional Study

These findings are consistent with prior literature highlighting the concept of uremic cardiomyopathy, a term encompassing cardiac hypertrophy, fibrosis, and systolic/diastolic dysfunction driven by CKD-related hemodynamic and metabolic stressors [2].

Left Ventricular Hypertrophy and Remodelling

LVH and cardiac remodelling are common in ESRD patients on haemodialysis, significantly increasing the risk of cardiovascular mortality. LVH is a compensatory response to increased hemodynamic load, often resulting in enlarged heart chambers and thickened walls. This condition is linked to multiple factors in ESRD, including hypertension, anaemia, fluid overload, and arteriovenous fistula [14]. LVH is highly prevalent in ESRD patients starting dialysis, with estimates ranging from 60% to 80%. The pathophysiology of LVH in ESRD is multifactorial: chronic volume overload, anaemia-induced high output states, pressure overload from hypertension, and increased afterload from arteriovenous fistulas all contribute [10,6].

Causes of Left Ventricular Hypertrophy in End Stage Renal Disease

Multiple interrelated factors contribute to the development of LVH in patients receiving haemodialysis. Hypertension increases afterload, leading primarily to concentric hypertrophy. Volume overload from fluid retention and high AVF flow increases preload, favouring eccentric hypertrophy. Anaemia augments cardiac output and further promotes eccentric remodelling. Additional contributors include secondary hyperparathyroidism, hypoalbuminemia, and hyperhomocysteinemia, which exacerbate myocardial stress and remodelling [14].

Remodelling involves changes in the size, shape, and function of the heart, including myocyte hypertrophy and fibrosis. LVH is an independent predictor of cardiovascular mortality and sudden cardiac death in ESRD patients on dialysis. Uremia can also contribute to LVH [2].

Clinical Significance of LVH

LVH is a strong predictor of heart attacks, strokes, heart failure, and sudden death in dialysis patients. LVH can lead to impaired heart function, making it less efficient at pumping blood. In our study, LVH was present in 58.3% of patients, similar to the prevalence reported in the USRDS database (60–75%) and the DOPPS (Dialysis Outcomes and Practice Patterns Study), which found a 74% prevalence of LVH in dialysis patients using echocardiographic criteria [7,5]. Glasscock et al. and Zoccali et al. have emphasized that such maladaptive hypertrophy is not merely compensatory but often associated with myocardial fibrosis and poor cardiovascular outcomes [14,10]. Importantly, studies such as the one by London et al. showed that regression of LVH is achievable through blood pressure control and improved dialysis adequacy, which correlated with improved survival [10]. Our finding that hypertensive patients had a

significantly higher LV mass and RWT supports the hypothesis that pressure overload remains a dominant factor in LV remodelling in dialysis patients.

Left Atrial Volume Index

In the ESRD patients undergoing haemodialysis, LAVI (Left Atrial Volume Index) is a significant indicator of cardiovascular health and mortality risk. Increased LAVI, reflecting left atrial enlargement, is associated with higher mortality rates and adverse cardiovascular events in this population [17]. Elevated LAVI in ESRD patients on haemodialysis has been shown to be an independent predictor of mortality and cardiovascular events. Conditions like LVH, pulmonary hypertension, and volume overload are common in ESRD patients on haemodialysis and can contribute to increased LAVI and adverse outcomes [17].

Haemodialysis can temporarily reduce left atrial size and improve some echocardiographic parameters, but the long-term effects of volume overload and other factors associated with haemodialysis can still lead to LAVI elevation and increased risk [17].

In our study, the mean LAVI was 30 ± 4.25 mL/m², and abnormal enlargement was significantly more common among hypertensive patients (60.7% vs. 22.0%, $p < 0.001$). This finding highlights the strong association between chronic pressure overload and atrial remodelling in patients with ESRD on haemodialysis.

Diastolic Dysfunction

In our study, diastolic dysfunction was present in 66.7% of patients, a prevalence comparable to reports from international cohorts, which range from 60% to 80% among haemodialysis patients [Cho 2013; Liu 2021; Park 2012]. This supports the concept that abnormal LV relaxation is nearly universal in ESRD, often preceding overt systolic dysfunction.

Pathophysiologically, the burden of chronic hypertension, LV hypertrophy, and volume overload contribute significantly. Anaemia and mineral metabolism disorders may also exacerbate myocardial stiffening through mechanisms involving oxidative stress, fibroblast activation, and vascular calcification [Nuhu 2018; Zhou 2021]. Notably, while conditions such as diabetes and anaemia are traditionally associated with cardiac remodelling, we did not find statistically significant associations. This may reflect our limited sample size, high baseline prevalence of these conditions reducing contrast, and the dominant effect of hypertension in this cohort.

Clinically, elevated left atrial volume index in patients with diastolic dysfunction further underscores chronic pressure overload and predicts adverse cardiovascular outcomes, including atrial fibrillation, heart failure hospitalization, and mortality [Tseng 2024]. These findings highlight the importance of routine echocardiographic monitoring,

Structural and Functional Echocardiographic Changes in Haemodialysis Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease: A Cross-Sectional Study

including strain analysis, to detect early myocardial dysfunction in dialysis patients.

Systolic Function and Global Longitudinal Strain (GLS)

In patients with ESRD on haemodialysis, GLS is a more sensitive indicator of subclinical left ventricular (LV) dysfunction than traditional measures like Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction (LVEF). Impaired GLS, often seen even with normal LVEF, can be an early sign of myocardial changes related to ESRD and dialysis, such as hypertrophy, fibrosis, and ischemia.

The study by Liu et al. investigated the frequency and risk factors of impaired left ventricular GLS in patients with ESRD using two-dimensional speckle-tracking echocardiography. The study found a high prevalence of impaired GLS in ESRD patients with preserved LVEF with over half (58%) exhibiting dysfunction defined as GLS <18%. Increased left ventricular mass index (LVMI) was independently associated with abnormal GLS, and LV geometry was also larger or thicker in those with impaired GLS [21].

Despite normal LVEF in 84% of our cohort, 70.8% had reduced GLS, with a mean of $12 \pm 3.09\%$. This aligns with recent studies that identified GLS as a more sensitive marker for subclinical systolic dysfunction in ESRD patients [22].

For example, Liu et al. demonstrated in a prospective cohort that haemodialysis patients had significantly impaired GLS despite preserved LVEF, and that reduced strain predicted mortality more accurately than EF [21]. Similarly, in the CRIC study (Chronic Renal Insufficiency Cohort), Park et al. found that reduced GLS correlated with both all-cause and cardiovascular mortality in CKD stages 3–5 [6].

Our findings reinforce the argument for incorporating strain imaging into the standard echocardiographic protocol for ESRD patients. This is especially important since standard EF measurements may mask early myocardial dysfunction, as supported by studies in both CKD and chemotherapy cardiotoxicity populations.

Right Heart and Pulmonary Pressures

In patients with ESRD undergoing haemodialysis, pulmonary hypertension (PH) and right heart dysfunction are common and can significantly impact patient outcomes. PH, characterized by elevated pulmonary artery pressure, is particularly prevalent in this population and is associated with increased mortality [25]. PH is significantly more common in ESRD patients on haemodialysis compared to the general population, with reported incidences ranging from 8.8% to 68.8% [26].

Right ventricular dysfunction, assessed by TAPSE, was abnormal in 8.7% of our cohort. This finding is consistent with early RV impairment typically associated with pulmonary hypertension and chronic volume overload [17]. The presence of pulmonary hypertension is strongly linked to the duration of haemodialysis treatment and the presence

of arteriovenous access, which is used to create a pathway for blood flow during dialysis [25].

PH can lead to right ventricular (RV) dysfunction, as the right ventricle has to work harder to pump blood against the elevated pulmonary pressure [25].

Pulmonary hypertension is a significant complication in ESRD patients undergoing haemodialysis, and it is closely linked to right heart dysfunction and increased mortality. Understanding the underlying mechanisms and implementing appropriate management strategies are crucial for improving patient outcomes [25].

Pericardial Effusion

Pericardial effusion, often described as small and hemodynamically insignificant, is found in a significant proportion of ESRD patients on haemodialysis. While uremic pericarditis (pericarditis occurring before or within 8 weeks of dialysis initiation) and dialysis-associated pericarditis (occurring after 8 weeks of dialysis) are unique to kidney disease patients, the exact causes remain unclear. Volume overload is also a contributing factor [26].

Small, hemodynamically irrelevant effusions generally don't require specific interventions, but moderate to severe effusions can lead to symptoms and potentially cardiac tamponade [25].

Pericardial effusion was found in 15% of our cohort patients, primarily small and clinically silent. These findings are in agreement with older reports suggesting that 13–38% of dialysis patients may have pericardial involvement, largely due to uremia or fluid shifts [25].

With improved dialysis adequacy, the incidence of large effusions and uremic pericarditis has declined [26].

Valvular Regurgitation

In patients with ESRD on haemodialysis, both mitral and tricuspid regurgitation are relatively common, often stemming from functional issues like cardiac dilatation due to fluid overload. These regurgitations can be significantly reduced or even disappear with aggressive ultrafiltration to manage fluid balance and blood pressure [27].

A significant portion of these valvular insufficiencies are considered functional, meaning they arise from changes in heart chamber size and shape rather than structural valve damage.

Studies have shown that aggressive ultrafiltration, which reduces fluid overload, can improve or even eliminate these regurgitations [27].

While often functional, structural valve abnormalities like calcification can also contribute to regurgitation in ESRD patients, and infective endocarditis is a risk in this population [27].

Mild mitral and tricuspid regurgitation were present in 16.7% and 8.3%, respectively. These are generally functional in nature, secondary to annular dilation or

Structural and Functional Echocardiographic Changes in Haemodialysis Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease: A Cross-Sectional Study

elevated pulmonary pressures, rather than primary valve disease.

Why Other Risk Factors Were Not Significant

Despite their known pathophysiological roles, anaemia, dyslipidaemia, and mineral metabolism disorders were not significantly associated with abnormalities in our study. Possible explanations include limited sample size, high background prevalence (reducing contrast), and effective medical management (e.g., Erythropoiesis-Stimulating Agents, phosphate binders, statins). Longitudinal studies may better capture their cumulative impact.

Implications for Practice and Future Research

This study emphasizes the utility of comprehensive echocardiography, including GLS and pulmonary pressure assessment, in identifying early cardiovascular risk in CKD patients. Strain imaging in particular allows clinicians to detect subclinical dysfunction and initiate cardioprotective strategies (e.g., beta-blockers, ACE inhibitors, ultrafiltration optimization).

Future prospective studies should examine whether serial echocardiographic monitoring combined with personalized interventions can reduce adverse cardiovascular outcomes in ESRD. Integration with biomarkers (e.g., NT-proBNP, troponin T) and advanced imaging (e.g., cardiac MRI) may further enhance risk stratification.

CONCLUSIONS

In this cross-sectional study of patients with end-stage renal disease on maintenance haemodialysis, we found a high prevalence of structural and functional cardiac abnormalities, most notably left ventricular hypertrophy, diastolic dysfunction, and impaired global longitudinal strain, despite preserved ejection fraction in the majority of patients. Hypertension emerged as the strongest clinical correlate of these changes, underscoring its central role in uremic cardiomyopathy.

Our findings reinforce the value of comprehensive echocardiographic evaluation, including strain imaging and left atrial volume index measurement, in the routine assessment of dialysis patients. Early identification of subclinical myocardial dysfunction provides an opportunity for intensified risk factor modification and closer cardiovascular surveillance.

Future prospective studies are warranted to evaluate whether echocardiography-guided management strategies can improve long-term cardiovascular outcomes in this high-risk population.

CLINICAL PERSPECTIVES

Competency in Medical Knowledge

Patients with end-stage renal disease on maintenance haemodialysis exhibit a high prevalence of structural and functional cardiac abnormalities, including left ventricular

hypertrophy, diastolic dysfunction, and impaired global longitudinal strain, even when ejection fraction is preserved. Hypertension is a key driver of these abnormalities, underscoring the importance of aggressive blood pressure control. Comprehensive echocardiographic evaluation, including strain imaging and left atrial volume index assessment, provides valuable diagnostic and prognostic information in this high-risk population.

Translational Outlook

Future prospective studies are needed to determine whether echocardiography-guided interventions, including optimization of blood pressure, volume status, and anaemia management, can reduce the progression of cardiac remodelling and improve survival in patients with ESRD on haemodialysis. Integration of strain imaging into routine clinical practice may allow earlier identification of subclinical myocardial dysfunction and enable timely initiation of cardioprotective strategies.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest. No external funding.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

This study has several limitations. First, it was a single-center, cross-sectional analysis with a relatively modest sample size, which may limit generalizability and statistical power to detect associations with less prevalent risk factors such as anemia or mineral metabolism disorders.

Second, echocardiographic measurements were performed at a single time point, and pre- versus post-dialysis timing was not standardized, which could affect load-dependent parameters such as LAVI and GLS.

Third, longitudinal follow-up data on cardiovascular outcomes were not collected, preventing assessment of the prognostic implications of the observed abnormalities.

Finally, the study did not assess inter-observer or intra-observer variability for GLS measurements, which may affect reproducibility, although strain imaging was performed using standardized vendor-specific software by experienced operators.

Future multicenter, prospective studies with larger sample sizes and longitudinal follow-up are needed to validate these findings and assess their prognostic impact.

Structural and Functional Echocardiographic Changes in Haemodialysis Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Structural and Functional Echocardiographic Changes in Haemodialysis Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease: A Cross-Sectional Study

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